

THE CURRENT STATE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SCHOOLS WHERE EDUCATION IS CONDUCTED IN RELATED LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to the analysis of the current state of English language teaching in schools where education is provided in related languages (Uzbek, Karakalpak, Kazakh, Turkmen). The research studies modern methodological approaches, existing problems and foreign experiences. It also develops practical recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of education.

Introduction

Today, learning English is one of the priorities of the global education system. Especially in schools where education is conducted in fraternal languages, the issue of teaching English requires a special scientific and methodological approach. Because in such an environment, students work with several language systems at the same time.

Scientific research conducted in Karakalpakstan shows that, although the English language teaching system is developing significantly, there is a need for methodological improvement. [1]

Also, foreign researchers emphasize that the process of language teaching in a multilingual environment is important in developing students' linguistic thinking. [2]

Related languages belong to the Turkic language family, and there are phonetic, lexical and grammatical similarities between them. These factors create the following situations in learning English:

1. positive transfer facilitates learning through similar structures;
2. negative transfer (interference) which leads to grammatical and syntactic errors.

For example, while in Turkic languages the sentence structure is usually in the form of SOV, in English the SVO model is used. This causes errors in the speech of students. [3]

Therefore, the comparative (contrastive) methodology is considered an effective tool in teaching English based on related languages. [4]

In the current education system, a number of modern methodological approaches are widely used in teaching English. In particular, the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach is aimed at developing students' skills in communicating freely in real-life situations, with the main emphasis on the practical use of language.

Also, through the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach, students simultaneously master both the language and the content of another subject, which allows them to learn the language in conditions close to the natural environment. Task-based learning (TBL) involves organizing the learning process on the basis of various practical tasks, in which students develop language skills by completing specific tasks.

In addition, the use of digital and interactive technologies is becoming an integral part of the educational process. These approaches are important in increasing student motivation, making lessons interesting, and ensuring an individual approach.

The communicative approach serves to develop students' real-life communication competence.

The CLIL methodology, on the other hand, comprehensively develops students' knowledge by integrating science and language. [5]

However, in practice, the dominance of the grammatical-translation method is still observed in many schools, which leads to insufficient development of speech activity. [6]

The analysis revealed the following main problems:

1. insufficient development of the educational and methodological base;
2. a lack of textbooks adapted to the related languages;
3. low level of teachers' use of modern methods;
4. the problem of interference in a multilingual environment.

According to research conducted in Karakalpak schools, national and linguistic characteristics are not sufficiently taken into account in teaching English.

In foreign experience, the following areas of English language teaching have been found to be effective:

1. Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL)
2. Learning Management Systems (Moodle, Google Classroom)
3. Blended learning
4. Adaptive learning technologies

Mobile learning technologies expand the opportunities for students to learn independently. [7]

Also, in modern education, the teacher acts as a facilitator, not a provider of knowledge.

Based on the results of the study, a number of important proposals and recommendations were developed. First of all, it was determined that there is a need to systematically introduce comparative methodology in teaching English, since this approach helps to effectively master the similarities and differences between sister languages. It is also important to create modern textbooks and teaching aids adapted to sister languages, taking into account the linguistic characteristics of students.

In addition, it is necessary to regularly improve the qualifications of teachers in order to develop their professional competence. The widespread use of digital technologies in the educational process was also recognized as one of the factors increasing efficiency. At the same time, it is recommended to increase the share of exercises focused on speech competence to develop students' practical language skills.

Conclusion

Although teaching English in schools where education is conducted in sister languages has its own complexities, high results can be achieved through effective methodological approaches.

The quality of education can be significantly improved by integrating modern pedagogical technologies, comparative methodology, and a communicative approach. In the future, the development of a special methodological system in this area is an urgent scientific task.

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